

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVITY OF FUTURE TEACHERS BASED ON THE PROJECT METHOD

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10581863>

Abstract. *This article provides information about the pedagogical possibilities of developing creativity in students and raising creative, initiative individuals using the project method, as well as the conditions for creating motives for the creative acquisition of professional knowledge, experience and competencies in students as a result of the use of project-based educational technologies. The project shows the methods of organizing students' educational activities in the process of using educational technologies. Students are provided with the knowledge, skills, qualifications, professional competencies and methods of activity necessary to work on the project problem.*

Keywords: *future teacher, project method, project educational technologies, creativity, creativity development, professional knowledge, formation of motives.*

Using the project method, the development of creativity among students, their independent learning, and the formation of their motivations are gaining special relevance. The project method is one of the leading methods for developing students' work skills in a new situation and attracting them to independent education. Because the project method makes it possible to train a creative, enterprising person. It is important to form the skills of a positive approach to the performance of educational tasks in students. Developing their independence in the process of making decisions, acquiring the skills to apply the acquired knowledge to practical activities and development of the environment is important in ensuring independence in students. Most students will not have enough experience working independently with educational literature. They find it difficult to perform mental operations such as finding the main idea from the text, drawing conclusions and summarizing. This is also related to the psychological characteristics of students. On the other hand, the process of applying knowledge to students in higher education institutions and its content, the nature of educational materials will change. As a result, students face difficulties in acquiring knowledge independently. They have insufficiently developed positive motives for the educational process. It is observed that the skills of working with educational materials and voluntary qualities are insufficiently developed in students. Students begin to feel tired and bored in classes. Such psychological conditions indicate a low level of self-management skills. It is known that high demands are placed on the educational activities of students in higher educational institutions. These students need to acquire the necessary methods for mental analysis of problems, acquire the necessary methods for mental analysis, acquire positive motives for mastering academic subjects, develop creativity, quickly adapt to the social lifestyle of the Uzbek people, learn creative experiences. requires the use of methods to create favorable conditions for development. Creative activity of students ensures that cognitive activity acquires a permanent character. As a result of involving students in creative activities, they will have holistic personal qualities related to creativity.

- mental activity;
- to be educated quickly;

- ability to show intelligence;
- inventiveness;
- manifestation of the ability to acquire new knowledge independently;
- applying acquired knowledge in new life situations;
- such as the development of motivation for the educational process.

Today, various regional innovative technologies are used in higher pedagogical education. These technologies serve to a certain extent to develop students' motivation for independent learning and creativity. One of the most productive technologies is project education technology. Significant pedagogical ideas and experiences can be embodied in project educational technology. The educational technologies of the project are primarily used in order to develop students' motives for independent learning, to encourage them to show creative activity. As a result of the use of project educational technologies, motivations for creative mastery of professional knowledge, experience and competences are created in students. Diagnosing each student's cognitive interests and abilities during tasks that allow to achieve this goal; directing students' knowledge interests to professional activities; development of motives for systematic acquisition of professional knowledge, skills, qualifications and competences among students; application of technologies necessary for searching, collecting and using professional information in the educational process; improvement of methods and conditions of acquisition of knowledge and experiences necessary for professional activity; modeling of technologies mastered by students; ensuring cooperation of students and professors in the educational process; development of students' qualities of conscientious approach to their profession; among students are responsibility, concern for the interests of the community, professional culture, initiative, development of aesthetic taste.

The following are the main principles of project educational technologies: relying on students' professional interests and existing knowledge reserves; providing students with a wide range of knowledge; directing students to professional activities of a creative nature; taking into account the needs of the state and society in the professional formation of students.

One of the main principles of educational technology is to take into account the social order and personal and professional interests of students. This principle directly requires students' professional development motives, interests, and the needs of the state and society to be fully taken into account. In the process of professional formation and development of students, directing the educational process to the realization of educational goals, organizing success situations for students, using simulation games based on the development of active and cognitive processes, introducing life situations into the educational process, interesting and the use of productive educational tasks, creation of a competitive environment among students is required.

In the process of using educational technologies, the project envisages the use of the method of organizing educational activities of students. Among such methods

1. Using creative assignments.
2. Creating problematic situations.
3. Use of activating exercises.
4. Performing heuristic tasks.
5. Work independently on practical tasks,
6. Such as the use of creative activity methods that are compatible with students directly in the course of educational activities.

Based on the educational technologies of the project, it is possible to control the development of independent work motives among students as follows:

- use of tests;
- use of classified requests;
- independent self-control;
- such as controlling each other

In order to develop students' activity, it is envisaged to use various types of work in situations outside the auditorium. Such situations can include participation in various competitions, participation in Olympiads, and participation in quizzes.

The educational technologies of the project aimed at stimulating creativity in students on the basis of independent learning allow them to think creatively, deepen their acquired knowledge, and apply this knowledge in new life situations. Diagnostic examination of the formation of motives for independent learning in students in such situations; use of different forms of work outside the audience; individual work with students, providing them with the necessary professional advice; promotion of independent creative works of students; participation in creative projects; perform final diagnosis; implies the formation of skills for regular correction of one's activities.

Along with their professional interests, psychological and pedagogical characteristics are of particular importance in the development of students' motives for independent learning. By determining the level of students' professional interests, it is possible to analyze the mechanisms of creativity development in them. Only then can students effectively develop the skills to work on project-based educational technologies.

It is possible to determine the degree of formation of motives for independent learning in students with the help of project educational technologies, using questionnaires, observation, interview organization, test control, and creative tasks. As a result of the development of independent learning motives and creative activity in students using educational technologies, the skills of creating models, layouts, essays, illustrations, drawings representing the results of creative activity are developed. As a result of the development of motives for independent learning in students, showing creative activity, successfully applying previously acquired knowledge in new situations, turning professional knowledge, skills, qualifications into experience of creative activity, successfully applying these experiences in various conditions and situations, professional it is intended to successfully combine the methods of activity, to find new methods and ways of completing tasks.

Algorithms for creating project educational technologies include the stages of presenting ideas, their implementation and reflection. At the initial stage, students put forward the ideas necessary to create the technology of the project. The topic of educational technologies of the project is formed based on the topics included in the educational module. This is one of the special problems of teaching based on project technology. In addition, the topic of the educational technology project should be proportional to the students' knowledge levels and established methods of activity. Students are required to carry out actions and activity methods based on their capabilities when completing the assigned tasks. It is appropriate to pay special attention to the independent work of requirements when working on the basis of project educational technologies. In this process, they apply the knowledge, skills, competences, professional competencies and methods of operation necessary to work on the project problem. In seminars and laboratory

sessions, students are required to work independently as much as possible, think creatively, and think deeply about each problem of the project. Theoretical information should be provided to students as a guide and foundation. Professors and teachers should use a number of methods to encourage students to work on the project. These include digital tools, presentation of theoretical information in the form of clusters, expanding the scope of practical training, seminars, laboratory training, and independent work. Students can make certain mistakes when working on the basis of project educational technologies. Professors and teachers are required to identify such mistakes in time and cooperate with students in eliminating them. In addition, it is of particular pedagogical importance that students independently find new methods and ways to solve the problem, and creatively approach the problem. The results of the work carried out show that in the process of working on the educational technologies of the project, students are ready for social life and professional activities, and successfully master the experience of creative activities.

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